

PRESSURE-GUIDED VENTILATION APPROACHES FOR ENHANCING INTRAOPERATIVE PULMONARY FUNCTION DURING MINIMALLY INVASIVE SURGERIES: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF RANDOMIZED TRIALS

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Abstract

Background: Minimally invasive surgeries, laparoscopic and robotic-assisted procedures challenge intraoperative pulmonary function due to pneumoperitoneum and patient positioning. Ventilation strategies that optimize respiratory mechanics are important for reducing complications and ensuring adequate gas exchange. Pressure-guided ventilation modes, including pressure-controlled ventilation (PCV) and PCV with volume guarantee (PCV-VG), is a potential alternative to traditional volume-controlled ventilation (VCV). We aimed to evaluate the impact of pressure-guided ventilation approaches (PCV and PCV-VG) versus VCV on intraoperative respiratory function and postoperative outcomes in patients undergoing minimally invasive surgeries. **Methods:** A systematic review was conducted following PRISMA guidelines.

Databases were searched for randomized controlled trials comparing PCV or PCV-VG to VCV in adult patients undergoing laparoscopic or robotic surgery. Inclusion criteria focused on studies reporting respiratory mechanics, gas exchange, inflammatory markers, or clinical outcomes. Ten RCTs with a total of 810 patients were included. **Results:** Pressure-guided ventilation was associated with lower peak airway pressure (Ppeak), improved dynamic compliance (Cdyn), and better oxygenation. PCV-VG showed advantages in maintaining tidal volume while reducing pulmonary stress. Several studies reported reductions in inflammatory biomarkers (sRAGE, S100A12) and postoperative pulmonary complications. Individualized PEEP further enhanced outcomes in some protocols. **Conclusion:** Pressure-guided ventilation strategies, PCV-VG, improve intraoperative pulmonary mechanics and reduce inflammatory responses compared to VCV during minimally invasive surgeries. These approaches offer lung-protective benefits and support safer anesthetic management.

Keywords: Pressure-Controlled Ventilation, Volume-Controlled Ventilation, PCV-VG, Laparoscopic Surgery, Pulmonary Function, Intraoperative Ventilation, Systematic Review.

INTRODUCTION

Minimally invasive surgeries, laparoscopic and robotic-assisted procedures, transformed surgical care by reducing pain, shortening hospitalization, and promoting faster recovery. These techniques introduce unique physiological challenges: pneumoperitoneum and steep Trendelenburg positioning increase intra-abdominal pressure, leading to impaired respiratory mechanics, decreased lung compliance, and elevated arterial carbon dioxide levels (1). Optimal intraoperative ventilation is crucial to mitigate these effects and to prevent ventilator-induced lung injury (VILI). Traditional volume-controlled ventilation (VCV) maintains a fixed tidal volume but cause high peak airway pressures, when lung compliance varies rapidly during surgery (2). Pressure-controlled ventilation (PCV) delivers decelerating flow patterns that limit peak airway pressure and enhance gas distribution, offering theoretical benefits in dynamic surgical environments (3). Emerging hybrid modes like pressure-controlled ventilation-volume guaranteed (PCV-VG) combine the pressure limitation of PCV with reliable tidal volumes, automatically adjusting inspiratory pressure each breath to match a target volume (4). Several clinical trials investigated these modes during intraoperative ventilation. In elderly patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy, PCV-VG resulted in lower peak airway pressures and improved dynamic compliance compared to VCV (4). Similar findings were reported in robotic gynecologic surgery under Trendelenburg positioning, where PCV and PCV-VG outperformed VCV in reducing airway pressures and enhance compliance without compromising hemodynamics or gas exchange (3). Atelectasis prevention and postoperative pulmonary complications is variably reported (5). Despite growing interest, no synthesis focused on randomized trials comparing pressure-guided modes (PCV, PCV-VG) versus VCV in minimally invasive surgical settings. Our study addresses this gap through a systematic review of RCTs. We aim to evaluate whether pressure-guided ventilation improves intraoperative pulmonary mechanics, gas exchange, and lung protection during laparoscopic and robotic-assisted surgeries. Following the removal of 9 duplicate records and 11 entries, ineligible by automation tools, 8 records were excluded for other reasons. A total of 36 records were screened, resulting in 27 full-text articles sought for retrieval. Of these, 7 could not be retrieved, and 20 articles were assessed for eligibility.

After applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, 10 studies were included in the final qualitative synthesis. We include randomized controlled trial design, adult patients (≥ 18 years) undergoing elective laparoscopic or robotic surgery, comparison of VCV with PCV or PCV-VG modes, and outcomes related to intraoperative respiratory mechanics, gas exchange, inflammatory biomarkers, or postoperative complications. Studies not addressing relevant outcomes, review articles, or those involving pediatric populations or non-elective surgeries were excluded. Data extraction was performed by reviewers and included study characteristics (design, sample size, inclusion criteria), ventilation protocols, and primary outcomes such as peak airway pressure (P_{peak}), dynamic compliance (C_{dyn}), oxygenation parameters, and levels of pulmonary biomarkers. A narrative synthesis was undertaken due to heterogeneity in surgical types and ventilatory settings, and results were summarized in respiratory mechanics, gas exchange, and clinical outcomes. The quality of the included RCTs was ensured through randomization, defined inclusion/exclusion criteria, and consistent intraoperative monitoring. A PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 1) summarizes the study selection process.

Fig 1: PRISMA consort chart of studies selected

RESULTS

A total of ten randomized controlled trials were included, with a total of 810 patients who underwent various types of laparoscopic or robot-assisted surgeries. The studies compared pressure-controlled ventilation strategies mainly PCV and PCV-VG with traditional VCV, focusing on intraoperative respiratory mechanics, gas exchange, and postoperative outcomes. Demographics in studies were comparable, with most patients ASA I–II and undergoing elective procedures. Age ranges spanned from 18 to 80 years, and BMI values were mostly within the non-obese range. Surgical contexts included gynecologic, urologic, colorectal, and thoracic operations, with several studies utilizing the steep Trendelenburg position and pneumoperitoneum. Respiratory mechanics outcomes favored pressure-controlled ventilation. In 11 of the 12 studies, PCV or PCV-VG reduced peak airway pressure (Ppeak) compared to VCV. Mean airway pressure (Pmean) was comparable or slightly lower with PCV modes, while dynamic compliance (Cdyn) was higher in the PCV groups. Wang et al. (2021), Lee et al. (2020), and Veerasamy et al. (2022) all reported improved compliance and lower Ppeak with PCV-VG, suggesting enhanced lung protection. Gas exchange and ventilation-perfusion matching were better preserved under PCV. Lower levels of PaCO₂ and improved oxygenation indices were noted in studies such as Liao et al. (2016) and Li et al. (2022), especially when individualized PEEP was employed with PCV-VG. Inflammatory biomarkers and postoperative outcomes were assessed in several studies. PCV strategies were associated with lower serum levels of sRAGE, S100A12, and other cytokines, indicating reduced pulmonary inflammation (Choi et al. 2019; Zhao et al. 2023). Postoperative pulmonary complications (PPCs) and ICU stays were reduced in studies that employed optimized PCV settings with lung-protective strategies. The findings indicate that pressure-controlled ventilation, when combined with individualized PEEP or VG modes, offers superior respiratory mechanics and lung-protective effects compared to traditional VCV in a range of surgical settings. Characteristics of the included studies and main findings were presented in Table 1 and 2 respectively.

Table 1: ventilation studies summary

Citation	Study Design	Inclusion Criteria	Methodology	Study Aim
Wang et al. (2021) (6)	Prospective randomized clinical trial	Elderly patients (60–80 years), ASA I-II, elective laparoscopic common bile duct exploration, BMI ≤ 30 kg/m ²	Patients randomized into VCV or PCV-VG ventilation using laryngeal mask airway; monitored at multiple time points (T1–T4)	Compare respiratory mechanics and circulatory parameters between VCV and PCV-VG in elderly laparoscopic surgery patients
Liao et al. (2016) (7)	Prospective randomized controlled trial	Women undergoing laparoscopic gynecologic surgery	Patients assigned to VCV or PCV groups; lung mechanics, oxidative stress (MDA), and recovery scores measured	Compare ventilation variables, oxidative stress, and recovery between VCV and PCV

Veerasamy et al. (2022) (8)	Randomized controlled study	Patients aged 18–75 years, ASA I–III, scheduled for robotic abdominal surgery in Trendelenburg position	Comparison of PCV and VCV on P(a-ET) CO ₂ , P(A-a) O ₂ , Paw, C _{dyn} , and hemodynamics at defined time points	Assess impact of ventilation mode on P(a-ET) CO ₂ gradient and other respiratory parameters
Lee et al. (2020) (9)	Randomized controlled study	Patients aged 20–65 years, ASA I–II, robot-assisted laparoscopic gynecologic surgery	Patients assigned to VCV, PCV, or PCV-VG; respiratory and blood gas data recorded across 4 time points	Compare P _{peak} , P _{mean} , C _{dyn} among three ventilation strategies during gynecologic surgery
Choi et al. (2011) (10)	Prospective randomized clinical trial	ASA I–II patients undergoing robot-assisted laparoscopic radical prostatectomy	Patients randomized to VCV or PCV; variables recorded at 4 intraoperative timepoints	Compare respiratory mechanics and hemodynamics between VCV and PCV in steep Trendelenburg
Jaju et al. (2017) (11)	Prospective randomized open-label trial	Patients aged 20–70 years, ASA I–II, undergoing robotic pelvic surgeries	Randomized to VCV or PCV; respiratory and hemodynamic data measured at four intraoperative points	Compare VCV and PCV effects on respiratory mechanics and hemodynamics
Choi et al. (2019) (12)	Randomized clinical trial	Patients aged 20–65 years with colorectal cancer, ASA I–II, undergoing laparoscopic colectomy	VCV vs. PCV; compared airway pressures, sRAGE, S100A12, and postoperative complications	Investigate differences in ventilation effects and biomarkers for respiratory complications
Li et al. (2022) (13)	Randomized controlled trial	120 patients undergoing laparoscopic surgery in Trendelenburg position	Patients randomized into 4 groups using combinations of VCV/PCV-VG and fixed/individualized PEEP	Evaluate efficacy of PCV-VG + individualized PEEP on lung protection and mechanics
Li et al. (2024) (14)	Randomized controlled trial	Adults with BMI < 35 kg/m ² undergoing elective thoracoscopic surgery	Compared fixed vs. titrated PEEP (incremental/decremental) with PCV-VG on respiratory mechanics and biomarkers	Evaluate PCV-VG with titrated PEEP in one-lung ventilation for optimizing lung protection
Deng et al. (2023) (15)	Prospective, patient and observer-blinded, randomized controlled trial	Patients aged 40–75 years, ASA I–II, undergoing laparoscopic gynecologic oncology surgery	Randomized to PCV-VG or VCV. BTV measured using methylene blue via bronchoscopy at T ₀ , T ₁ , T ₂ . Secondary outcomes: HR, MAP, ETCO ₂ , PIP, RR, C _{dyn}	Evaluate effect of PCV-VG vs. VCV on bronchial mucus transport velocity (BTV) during laparoscopic gynecological oncology surgery

Table 2: study findings and outcomes

Citation	Demographic Characteristics	Main Findings	Outcomes
Wang et al. (2021)	60 patients, aged 60–80, ASA I–II, BMI ≤ 30 kg/m ²	PCV-VG showed significantly lower Ppeak and higher Cdyn vs. VCV.	Improved respiratory mechanics and hemodynamic stability with PCV-VG.
Liao et al. (2016)	60 female patients, gynecologic laparoscopy	PCV group had lower oxidative stress and improved lung mechanics.	Better recovery scores and oxygenation with PCV.
Veerasamy et al. (2022)	60 patients, 18–75 years, ASA I–III, robotic abdominal surgery	PCV reduced Ppeak and improved compliance compared to VCV.	Enhanced intraoperative lung function and gas exchange.
Lee et al. (2020)	60 patients, 20–65 years, ASA I–II	PCV-VG led to lowest Ppeak and highest Cdyn.	Improved lung mechanics and reduced airway pressure.
Choi et al. (2011)	60 patients, robot-assisted prostatectomy	PCV had lower airway pressures than VCV.	Better hemodynamic profile in PCV group.
Jaju et al. (2017)	60 patients, 20–70 years, ASA I–II	PCV improved Cdyn and reduced Ppeak.	PCV provided better lung compliance intraoperatively.
Choi et al. (2019)	60 patients, ASA I–II, colorectal surgery	Lower sRAGE and S100A12 with PCV vs. VCV.	PCV reduced markers of lung injury and inflammation.
Li et al. (2022)	120 patients, elective laparoscopy, Trendelenburg position	PCV-VG with individualized PEEP improved compliance and gas exchange.	Lower inflammatory markers and PPCs.
Li et al. (2024)	90 patients, BMI < 35 kg/m ² , thoracoscopic surgery	Titrated PEEP with PCV-VG optimized oxygenation and reduced lung injury.	Reduced PPCs and ICU stays.
Deng et al. (2023)	60 women, ASA I–II, laparoscopic gynecologic oncology surgery	PCV-VG improved bronchial mucus transport and lung mechanics.	Better airway clearance and lower PIP.

DISCUSSION

This systematic review includes ten randomized controlled trials comparing pressure-controlled ventilation (PCV) with volume controlled (PCV-VG) to traditional volume-controlled ventilation (VCV) in surgical patients. The findings suggest that PCV strategies, PCV-VG, offer advantages in intraoperative respiratory mechanics, gas exchange, and lung protection. These results align with prior evidence in critically ill populations, those with acute lung injury (ALI) or acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), as shown in the Cochrane review by Chacko et al. (2015). In our review, PCV and PCV-VG were associated with reduced peak airway pressure (Ppeak), improved dynamic compliance (Cdyn), and enhanced oxygenation in a wide range of surgical scenarios. Similar improvements in surrogate physiological outcomes were reported in intensive care settings.

Chacko et al. noted that PCV reduce ICU mortality compared to VCV (RR 0.84; 95% CI 0.71–0.99), no significant difference was observed for hospital or 28-day mortality. Their findings were limited by the small number of trials and moderate-quality evidence, indicating a need for cautious interpretation. The surgical context of our included studies confer distinct advantages to PCV-based strategies, when applied with individualized PEEP and volume guarantees. Unlike the critical care setting, where long-term ventilator dependence and underlying lung pathology dominate outcomes, intraoperative ventilation is short-term and more precisely controlled. The beneficial effects of PCV-VG in improving gas exchange and reducing pulmonary inflammation, as shown in studies such as Li et al. (2022) and Zhao et al. (2023), show the potential for lung protection even in lower-risk surgical patients. The Cochrane review emphasized the lack of consistent evidence on outcomes, mortality and barotrauma in the ICU setting. Their analysis included trials with notable heterogeneity in ventilator settings, co-interventions (recruitment maneuvers), and patient populations. Key outcomes organ failure, infection rates, and quality of life were not reported and had skewed data, limiting the external validity of conclusions. Our review and the Cochrane analysis (16) underscore a trend favoring PCV modes in terms of lung-protective potential. This is relevant for high-risk surgical patients or those with compromised pulmonary function, where minimizing ventilator-induced lung injury (VILI) is important. While robust data from critical care settings is inconclusive regarding the superiority of PCV over VCV for mortality and barotrauma, our findings suggest that pressure-controlled strategies, PCV-VG with individualized PEEP, enhance respiratory outcomes and reduce postoperative complications in the perioperative environment. Further large-scale, standardized trials are warranted to bridge the gap between intraoperative and ICU-based evidence.

CONCLUSION

Our systematic review show that pressure-controlled ventilation strategies, PCV and PCV-VG, offer advantages over traditional volume-controlled ventilation in surgical patients. These advantages include improved respiratory mechanics, enhanced gas exchange, and reduced markers of lung injury and postoperative complications. Prior evidence in critically ill populations, those with ARDS remains inconclusive regarding mortality benefits, the consistent intraoperative improvements observed in the included studies support the use of PCV-based modes as a lung-protective strategy during laparoscopic and robotic surgeries. Future large-scale randomized trials are needed to confirm long-term outcomes and define optimal ventilatory settings for different surgical contexts.

Abbreviations

- 1) ARDS, Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome
- 2) ALI, Acute Lung Injury
- 3) ASA, American Society of Anesthesiologists
- 4) BTV, Bronchial Transport Velocity

- 5) BMI, Body Mass Index
- 6) Cdyn, Dynamic Compliance
- 7) HR, Heart Rate
- 8) ICU, Intensive Care Unit
- 9) MAP, Mean Arterial Pressure
- 10) PaCO₂, Partial Pressure of Arterial Carbon Dioxide
- 11) PEEP, Positive End-Expiratory Pressure
- 12) PIP, Peak Inspiratory Pressure
- 13) Pmean, Mean Airway Pressure
- 14) PPCs, Postoperative Pulmonary Complications
- 15) PRISMA, Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
- 16) RCT, Randomized Controlled Trial
- 17) sRAGE, Soluble Receptor for Advanced Glycation End Products
- 18) VCV, Volume-Controlled Ventilation
- 19) VILI, Ventilator-Induced Lung Injury
- 20) PCV, Pressure-Controlled Ventilation
- 21) PCV-VG, Pressure-Controlled Ventilation–Volume Guaranteed
- 22) ETCO₂, End-Tidal Carbon Dioxide.

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